

Architecture document

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List of abbreviations

<i>AAI</i>	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
<i>AES</i>	Advanced Encryption Standard
<i>API</i>	Application Programming Interface
<i>C_i</i>	Control interface
<i>C_iGUMan</i>	Control interface Graphical UserManager
<i>C_iServManQMan</i>	Control interface ServiceManager QueryManager
<i>C_iServSec</i>	Control interface Service Security
<i>C_iStDSync</i>	Control interface StorageManager DataSynchronize
<i>C_iStManDMan</i>	Control interface StorageManager DataManager
<i>C_iStSec</i>	Control interface Storage Security
<i>C_iUSec</i>	Control interface User Security
<i>CKAN</i>	Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network
<i>CRUD</i>	Create, Read, Update, Delete
<i>DAC</i>	discretionary access control
<i>DCAT-AP</i>	Data Catalogue Application Profile
<i>D_i</i>	Data interface
<i>D_iDManCSt</i>	Data interface DataManager CentralStore
<i>D_iStServ</i>	Data interface Storage Service
<i>D_iStSyncDMan</i>	Data interface StorageSynchronize DataManager
<i>D_iStSyncLR</i>	Data interface StorageSynchronize LocalRepository
<i>D_iUServ</i>	Data interface User Service
<i>DOI</i>	Digital Object Identifiers
<i>DQV</i>	Data Quality Vocabulary
<i>ELN</i>	Electronic Lab Notebook
<i>GDPR</i>	General Data Protection Regulation
<i>GUI</i>	Graphical User Interface

<i>HTML</i>	HyperText Markup Language
<i>HTTP</i>	HyperText Transfer Protocol
<i>IaC</i>	Infrastructure As Code
<i>ISBN</i>	International Standard Book Number
<i>JSON-LD</i>	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
<i>KMS</i>	Key Management Service
<i>MFA</i>	Multi-factor authentication
<i>MU</i>	Machine-understandable
<i>OAI-PMH</i>	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
<i>OIDC</i>	OpenID Connect
<i>ORCID</i>	Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier
<i>PID</i>	Persistent identifiers
<i>RAM</i>	Random access memory
<i>RDBMS</i>	Relational Database Management System
<i>RDF</i>	Resource Description Framework
<i>RDM</i>	Research Data Management
<i>REST</i>	Representational State Transfer
<i>SAML</i>	Security Assertion Markup Language
<i>SPARQL</i>	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
<i>SWORD</i>	Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit
<i>TRL</i>	Technology Readiness Levels
<i>URI</i>	Uniform Resource Identifier
<i>UUID</i>	Universally unique identifier
<i>XML</i>	Extensible Markup Language

1. Introduction

Project objective

The community of catalysis researchers works rather isolated from the point of view of Research Data Management (RDM), which is partly due to guidelines on intellectual property imposed by cooperation partners from industry. In addition, surveys have shown that there is currently an insufficient digitization of data [Mendes et al., 2020]. All this leads to the low level of exchange of information and results or its absence, which causes a general slowdown in further effective development in this area.

Thus, the goal of this project is to create a research data infrastructure for the national community of catalysis researchers. This infrastructure aims to improve the data management and ensure an efficient research data life cycle. Within the framework of this project, it is planned to implement a central solution that all participants will be able to use. In addition, this infrastructure should also provide well-defined interfaces to connect to already existing solutions.

The project will use the agile methodology, so the document at hand will be iterated and, therefore, regularly expanded and updated as new requirements¹ are identified based on stakeholders' input.

Document structure

The document consists of two parts. The ***first part*** describes the general architecture of the proposed infrastructure. Here, the main blocks of the architecture are schematically presented, and the interaction between them is described. Special attention is paid to the flow and coordination of information between the blocks. The second part is devoted to the technical details of each main block.

Chapter 2.1 is devoted to the description of GUIs on user's layer for interaction between the main global parts of the system, such as local and central repositories, metaportal, service layer. Such approach provides more flexibility for the users and developers.

Since the main idea of the project is the efficient use and exchange of scientific and research information, data and metadata are important parts of the described infrastructure. Therefore, Chapter 2.2 is devoted to the description of the implementation of basic operations with research data and metadata, such as analysis, visualization and statistics using additional tools (collected as a toolbox). In addition, attention is paid to the communication tools between researchers aimed at the exchange of data and the ability to comment, share and reuse the results. This also touches many important aspects, such as search, identification, import and export, as well as a full data and metadata management throughout the entire life cycle.

Chapter 2.3 is devoted to the description of data storage and metadata, protocols for their synchronization. The structure of the repositories and a description of the interfaces that considers needs of users are also given.

Authorized access to data and metadata, their correct and secure use, as well as an access to individual blocks of the system is crucial. The implementation of the user verification mechanism, a clear delineation of user's access rights, is discussed in detail in Chapter 2.4.

¹ NFDI4Cat: Requirements Analysis. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7729748>, accessed on 17.03.2023.

Chapter 2.5 shows overall NFDI4Cat structure with interaction between all the layers.

The **second part** of the architecture document presents the planned implementation of the project architecture, considering the main software and hardware resources, as well as the functional and non-functional requirements, satisfying all the needs of the end user.

In Chapter 3 the planned Metaportal is described as well as its sub components implementing metadata quality validation (metrics), statistical analysis and other additional tools.

The detailed structure, implementation approach, and rationale for choosing the software for the central and local repositories are described in Chapters 4 and 5.

Since metadata handling is a key aspect of the NFDI4Cat project, special attention is paid to the semantic repository. Chapter 6 is devoted to a description of the mechanism that allows to store, query and process metadata, as well as to quickly access and implement new metadata schemas or ontologies.

Information resources (publications, data sets, individual studies, sets of metadata, other resources) must have a unique name to allow it to be identifiable and traceable. Chapter 7 describes the mechanism for automatically generating PIDs using the proposed PID manager, its implementation at the repository level, and how it interacts with the rest of the system.

The last part of the document (Chapter 8) describes the deployment of all components discussed in the previous chapters, considering hardware and software capabilities and features of the system.

Part 1: Architecture Specification

Part 1 of the Architecture Document provides a comprehensive description of the high-level design of a system. This part is divided into several subchapters, each of which focuses on a specific aspect of the system's architecture. The subchapters cover the user layer, service layer, storage layer, and security layer, providing detailed information about the different components and their functions. The user layer section describes the different user interfaces, including the Central and Local Repositories GUI, Meta Portal GUI, and Service Layer GUI. The service layer section covers general aspects of metadata organization, the metadata manager, ontology manager, query manager, transformer, PID manager, exporter, and importer, as well as collection of tools. The storage layer and security layer sections describe the storage and security infrastructure of the system, including authentication, authorization, encryption, and monitoring.

2. High-level Design

The NFDI4Cat consortium envisions to transform catalysis research across different disciplines in catalysis with the help of digitization. Towards this objective, we plan to cover the whole research data lifecycle with the help of emerging computer and data science techniques. In order to realize this vision, we need to identify and define the necessary building blocks. Figure 2-1 depicts our overall architecture.

Figure 2-1. NFDI4Cat overall architecture

The described architecture is organized into four key layers namely;

User Layer (U), **Service Layer (Serv)**, **Storage Layer (St)** and **Security Layer (Sec)**. Interaction among these layers is accomplished with the help of two interfaces namely: the *data interface (D_i)* and the *control interface (C_i)*. The **User Layer** ensures that end users can upload their research data, search the data uploaded by other users with the help of portals. It also provides Web tools to analyze and visualize the results of their analysis. The **Service Layer** ensures context-aware data and the associated metadata is available to the end user. It provides a complete life-cycle management of data and metadata from the time it is created until it is archived or deleted. The main functionality of the **Storage Layer** is to provide persistent data storage. It is responsible for managing the physical storage of data, ensuring data consistency and integrity, providing efficient access to stored data and metadata. These data stores are administrated by the hosting research institutes and structured according to their institutional specifications. The **Security Layer** ensures that the data and metadata is accessible to the intended recipient (individual end users or groups). More detailed information about each layer along with their components and functionality will be described in the following Chapters.

2.1 User Layer

The **User Layer** aims to provide the end users a responsive and intuitive way to interact with the underlying system. In this application, the main focus is on a simple and user understandable interface allowing interaction between users, data access and using of basic analysis tools. As shown in Figure 2-2, the software components of the User Layer is focused especially on the control of communication between the User Layer and other Layers. The interface *C_iGUMan* and *C_iUsec* is used for control and the interface *D_iUServ* is used for data exchange. The architecture is designed to be modular and expandable, and to support features that are needed to meet the high usability demands set by software and operating environments of the user interface.

Figure 2-2. Scheme of the User Layer architecture

The heart of the User Layer is the Web-based Graphical User Interface (GUI) core modules which are available for using the central and local repositories as well as the meta portal.

Service layer modules make the services at the Service Layer accessible. It is planned to setup all GUI components in such a way, that decisions made in the design don't set limitations on the usage of the existing software.

2.1.1 Central and Local Repositories GUI

A Graphical User Interface (GUI) is a type of software that allows users to interact with a system in a visual and intuitive way. In the context of a global repository and local repositories, a GUI would be used to manage and access the data that is stored within these repositories.

A global repository is a centralized location where data is made available to users from all the participating institutions. It is typically managed by a central institution (within the NFDI4Cat - HLRS), and is designed to provide a unified and consistent interface for accessing data from a wide range of sources. The GUI for a global repository would allow users to search, explore and access data, as well as making available own data contributions.

Local repositories, on the other hand, are smaller, more localized collections of data that are hosted by individual institutions or organizations. These repositories may have a more specialized focus, and are typically used to store and share data within a specific community. The GUI for a local repository allows users to access and manage the data within the repository, and may also include features for data sharing and collaboration within the local community.

In general, both the global and local repositories GUI's should be user-friendly, easy to use and navigate, and provide a consistent and intuitive interface for managing and accessing data. The GUI should also be designed to be flexible and adaptable, allowing for easy integration with other systems and software.

The NFDI4Cat project will host a central repository for users, and in the absence of local infrastructure, local repositories may also be provided by project partners. These local repositories will be integrated into the entire infrastructure through interfaces. Users can directly interact with these repositories, e.g. via GUI components. According to local data access rules and data access policies it will be manually decided, which metadata and data will be published in local repositories and which one will be published in the central repository.

2.1.2 Meta Portal GUI

On top of the distributed repository landscape the meta portal has an important role within the whole infrastructure, it aggregates the content of the local and central repositories by harvesting (parts of) the metadata of the provided data sets. This enables the users to search and explore the provided metadata. In addition, the meta portal includes different components that provide the possibility to analyze and visualize the collected metadata. A detailed description of the structure and functionality of the meta portal can be found in further chapters within the implementation part.

2.1.3 Service Layer GUI

Similar as repositories have own GUI components and can be accessed by the users directly, some of the Service Layer components can also have a GUI part which will also allow a direct interaction with them. This approach of separating GUI components provides more flexibility for the users and developers. On the one side, the service level components are integrated into the whole infrastructure via interfaces, that allows users to create sophisticated workflows with

many different steps. On the other side, it is possible for users also to interact with the components directly and separately, e.g. to perform some one-time activity instead of a complete workflow.

2.1.4 User Manager

The User Manager acts as a link between the **User Layer** and **Security Layer**. It uses the control interface *C_iUsec* to efficiently control users' activity and monitor their access. Section 2.4 describes in details different security access levels and permissions that will governs and limit user's view of data.

2.2 Service Layer

The **Service Layer** involves the following key components: metadata manager, ontology manager, query manager, file transformer, PID manager and toolbox consisting of several tools. The interaction among them is accomplished by the control interface *C_iServManQMan* and the data interface *D_iStServ*. Figure 2-3 provides a schematic view of the **Service Layer** components together with their main functionalities that will be described in this chapter. We note that metadata, and in particular semantic linkage of metadata, plays a central role in the entire NFDI4Cat initiative.

Figure 2-3. Service Layer Architecture

Therefore, the metadata manager will be described in more detail compared to other components.

2.2.1 General aspects of metadata organization

Below, some essential aspects of the data/metadata organization and workflow will be highlighted, starting from their origin at the local storage. First, a user collects all relevant data

within a self-contained research step. In general, the results of this study are collected in data sets which are saved to files or a database at a scientific instrument, to a user's PC, or a computational facility. In the vast majority of cases, these data are duplicated on a local server for a long-term storage that could eventually play the role of the local institute data storage. Before ingesting the data into the central (local) repository one (users, data provider) has to supplement them with appropriate metadata specifying the context of the data in a human- and machine-understandable (MU) form. Various descriptive and technical metadata fields are sometimes available in the headers of the corresponding instrument-generated data files. Quite often such metadata are inaccessible due to proprietary file formats. They are typically not MU-conform, because they do not employ common vocabularies that are well documented. At the same time, the metadata related e.g. to the description of the overall workflow, synthesis details are generally represented in non-unified and not very systematic way via paper lab journals, ELNs, MSExcel(R) sheets, etc.. However, such metadata are particularly crucial for the understanding and reusability of other data generated in a given research step. Therefore, such metadata should be ideally specified via ontologies which is currently not at all done in catalysis.

One of the results of the requirements analysis is that the semantic metadata description should be organized as an independent layer to the existing data infrastructure that ideally does not disturb the way the data is stored locally. In this respect, it is suggested that the metadata for a given research step is encapsulated within a so-called "metaset", that is a collection of appropriately structured metadata organized at a separate location. In general, each metaset would represent a certain subset of interconnected research steps as illustrated in Figure 2-4.

Figure 2-4. Metasets in relations to experimental steps

There is a degree of arbitrariness on how a whole research study (e.g. within a publication scope) is partitioned into metasets. It should not matter as long as all metadata are consistently interlinked in the semantic layer. For the global semantic searchability and unambiguous understanding of scientific data it is necessary to provide a formal specification of the metadata based on a shared conceptualization of the corresponding domain by means of ontologies. Therefore, the metadata should be represented in a suitable data model. We selected the Resource Description Framework (RDF²) data model which organizes the data as a set of triple statements involving relevant resources that are the instances of the classes defined in respective ontologies. The RDF data model provides a possibility for the semantic linkage of various entities involved in different studies, which is in particular achieved by combining the usage of the same URI³ (Uniform Resource Identifier) for identical resources with the semantic

² Resource Description Framework (RDF). https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Resource_Description_Framework, accessed on 19.12.2022.

³ Uniform Resource Identifier (URI). https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Uniform_Resource_Identifier, accessed on 13.02.2023.

expressivity of the RDF model by means of ontology. In principle, an RDF metaset can be serialized in a number of file formats, including XML, Turtle⁴. JSON-LD, etc. However, there can be many reasons to split it into multiple files, which is technically irrelevant for the triplestore⁵. For instance, this splitting would enable a very flexible control of the access rights to different parts of metadata.

It is suggested that the metasets would involve references to all locations of storage of the related data, including local repositories. In this case, as soon as the data is copied/moved to a new location, it should be indicated in the corresponding metaset. In this respect, one has to ensure a bidirectional association between primary and secondary data, primary and secondary metadata, as well as between primary data and metadata and secondary data and metadata. Furthermore, it is supposed that in general the data sets and metasets are relatively decoupled with respect to their physical location/flow. This is the case due to many reasons. In particular, the metasets have a complex structure, and can be continuously improved, supplemented with new information (even after publishing), whereas the data itself is more static in this respect. Secondly, while there is a need on shared work and version control on metasets, it seems to be hardly relevant for primary data. It does not make sense to version a data set being substituted or deleted if it is irrelevant or erroneous. On the other hand, if a data set is modified (by adding, changing or deleting files) then it can be easily tracked via the corresponding metaset in which these changes are reflected.

Last but not least, each metaset version will be provided with its own URI. This enables a straightforward findability of the research results, as well as easy navigation between the metasets.

2.2.2 Metadata manager

Figure 2-5. Service Layer - Metadata Manager

A partial view on the Metadata Manager is provided in Figure 2-5. Apart from a general framework for handling metadata, the metadata manager will encapsulate the following

⁴ Terse RDF Triple Language (Turtle). [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Turtle_\(syntax\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Turtle_(syntax)), accessed on 19.12.2022.

⁵ Triplestore. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Triplestore>, accessed on 19.12.2022.

functions: generation and validation of metaset, data set upload from a local storage to a repository, version control of metadata, as well as the user feedback. Below, these functions are considered in some more detail.

Generation and validation of metaset. In general, the generation of a metaset is a non-trivial process that can be self-dependently accomplished by a user only in relatively simple cases, even for user-friendly serializations like Turtle. Another aspect is the uniqueness of the generated metadata. This would mean that two scientists performing the same study independently should supplement it with the same set of metadata which conforms to certain standards. This will be ensured by a special interactive software which inquires the metadata according to the ontology specification. In principle, the software for validating metaset will employ similar algorithms. Thus, this functionality has the dependency on the ontology module. It is supposed to be implemented for the central and local repositories.

Links to data sets. Although this functionality deals with data sets, it is assigned to the metadata manager since all locations/serializations of a particular data set, starting from the local storage, are supposed to be indicated in the corresponding metaset, which would enable a better control of the data provenance.

Version control of metaset. The version control has two connected layers. The first one involves the versioning of the published metaset. It will be implemented for the repositories. The second one is designated for the curation of the metaset, and will be available only for the repository. There are many reasons to use version control even for a single user (tracking, reverting changes, etc.), and it is even more crucial in the case of shared work. In general, jointly working on metaset in a “coediting” mode is error-prone. Therefore, it should be coordinated via a version control system. In addition, there might be a need to have distinct versions of published metaset for different user groups for a flexible control of access rights to different parts of metadata.

User feedback. This functionality would provide an opportunity to share comments and critique on the published metaset. It is supposed to be implemented for the repository.

2.2.3 Ontology manager

This module involves the following functionalities in relation to the ontologies: validation, lookup service, version control, as well as user feedback.

Ontology validation. This functionality assumes the application of different tools for analyzing whether the ontology conforms to certain standards and ontology modeling best practices. Typically, it will be run before publishing an ontology in the repository.

Ontology lookup service. This feature will allow efficient search of the NFDI4Cat and external ontologies for different concepts, their relations and definitions, which would be particularly required for consistent use of the vocabularies for creating RDF metadata. It will be available in the repository.

Version control of ontology. As in the case of the metaset, the ontology versioning has two connected layers. The first one involves the versioning of the published ontologies. It will be available and published in some publication repository (the central repository or Zenodo⁶). The

⁶ Zenodo, publication repository. <https://zenodo.org/>, accessed on 14.12.2022.

second one is dedicated to the ontology development and will be available in a code repository such as GitHub or GitLab.

User feedback. This functionality plays an important role in the development and validation of the NFDI4Cat ontology and will be used by the place, where ontology is stored. It will be realized on the both mentioned above layers - within the level of the publication repository (for ontology versioning) and the GitHub or GitLab (for ontology development).

2.2.4 Query manager

The query manager offers a standardized query interface for performing federated queries on the metadata (e.g. a SPARQL endpoint) as well as navigation of metadata. This module can be invoked in different contexts, like simple searches as well as linking metadata to some external resources (as required in the metadata manager for the generation of metaset). While the SPARQL protocol offers very powerful means for searching various resources to experts, there are also other more intuitive features planned that enable a more convenient navigation through various resources to address a broad audience. This will be achieved via hyperlinking the identifiers in metaset by means of appropriate software. Similar feature can be provided for hyperlinking the classes used in metaset to the resources containing the definition of the corresponding ontology. In addition, an arbitrary combination of URIs for some known resources can be used as a search criterion. These and other possibilities for the lookup of metadata can be very useful in many contexts. In principle, it implies an ELN-like functionality for searching metadata, which is however available not only at the local level, but can interconnect data from many institutions. It is expected that appropriately chosen indexing which considers the sparsity of the metadata linkage can substantially improve the performance of the querying service. This module will be implemented for the metaportal and repository.

2.2.5 Transformer

This module handles the transformation of the RDF metadata files into appropriately structured HTML files for hyperlinking metaset, which is used by the query manager for navigating metadata. Herewith, there are two types of transformations:

- **RDF-to-HTML (formal).** This file transformation mainly supplements the RDF metaset with necessary hyperlinks, and at the same time preserve its triple structure.
- **RDF-to-HTML (informal).** In this case the formally specified metadata are converted into an informal (natural language) hypertext for a user-friendly navigation.

2.2.6 PID manager

This service is responsible for the assignment and storage of resolvable persistent identifiers (PIDs), which are normally used for unique references to publications, data sets, individual researches, and institutes, but can also be applied to other resources. An automatic generation of PIDs for file assets can be implemented at the repository level, as, e.g., in the case of Dataverse which integrates external handle infrastructure. With respect to the semantic layer, one has to consider the problem in more detail. Each triple statement in an RDF file involves at least one identifier representing some resource. In general, it should always be resolved if

someone looks up the corresponding URI. By construction, it consists of a namespace prefix followed by a local identifier. It is still disputable how exactly these entities should be assigned. However, it seems reasonable to derive the rules for a well-defined correspondence between the names of the local identifiers and the ontology classes which instances they represent. This can be done either manually or automatically by using the software for the generation of the RDF metadata. In this case, an external PID should only be provided for the namespace prefix of the ontology.

The PID manager is expected to be implemented for the repositories. In addition, it will have a close interplay with the Metadata and Query managers.

2.2.7 Exporter and Importer

These services help the users to upload their data and metadata to the central and to the different local repositories. Support of different file formats is required by the users here. Also a tight connection with the metadata manager must be realized, the data should be uploaded together with the metadata, or at least as sequential events inside one workflow (e.g. at the first step the data itself is uploaded creating a new repository entry, and then at the second step the metadata just be stored or edited for this new entry).

2.2.8 Harvester

The Harvester service is responsible for collecting metadata from different endpoints in one place. Currently it is supposed, that harvester will be integrated into the meta portal, and collection of the metadata will be done from all local as well as from the central repositories. In the project will be also investigated, if other harvesting components must be implemented into NFDI4Cat infrastructure.

2.2.9 Indexer

To realize searching functionality for data or metadata some indexing solution is needed. It is planned to setup several Indexer services, for every component that has an integrated search mechanism - metadata manager, local and central repositories, meta portal. The indexers can have different implementation and can be also unrelated to each other.

2.2.10 Registry

To keep represented in RDF metadata in harmonized way and to allow highly efficient searching functionality within the metadata some registry can be used, for every related component a separate one. The Registry services can be found in the metadata manager and in the meta portal - as completely independent from each other components.

2.2.11 General aspect of the Toolbox functionality

Some of the general functionality examples can be applied to all the proposed layers. The functionalities applied across all levels of an architecture includes data management, data integration, data processing and analysis, and data security and privacy. Additionally, the implementation of these functionalities may involve the use of different tools and technologies. Among those tools are **statistics tools**, **analysis tools** and **communication tools** description of which can be found in Chapter 3, and **visualization tools** which are described next.

Visualization Tools

Visualization tools provide scientists with an easier way to create visual representations of large data sets. When dealing with data sets that include hundreds of thousands of data points, automating the process of demonstrating information, makes the user's job significantly easier.

The appropriate data visualization tools must be chosen based on the following characteristics. First is their ease of use. There are some complicated instruments available for visualizing data. Some have excellent documentation and tutorials and are designed in ways that feel intuitive to the user. Others are lacking in those areas. The focus of the tools used should be on user-friendliness.

2.2.12 Service Manager

The Service Manager acts as a link between the **Service Layer** and **Security Layer**. It uses the control interface $C_iServSec$ to efficiently control service endpoint activity and monitor their access. Section 2.4 describes in details different security access levels and permissions that will governs and limit user's interactions with data and metadata.

2.3. Storage Layer

As mentioned in Chapter 1 the **Storage Layer** facilitates the flow of data and metadata between a local repository hosted at various participating institutes and the central repository. In order to enable interoperation the **Storage Layer** will support open protocols to synchronize data and metadata. NFDI4Cat has planned to host one central repository at High Performance Computing Center Stuttgart (HLRS). The central repository will be data agnostic to ensure that both data and metadata along with its semantic information can be stored and retrieved. To protect data and metadata integrity the **Storage Layer** provides four key components, namely *Storage Manager*, *Storage Synchronizer*, *Data Manager* and *Central Store*. Figure 2-6 shows the four components along with their interfaces.

Figure 2-6. Storage Layer structure

The *Storage Manager* is a link between the **Storage Layer** and **Security Layer**. It is responsible for the overall management of the central Store. It has three control interfaces

(*C_iStSec*, *C_iStManDMan*, *C_iStDSync*). These control interfaces ensure secure and authorized data and metadata synchronization. The *Storage Synchronizer* is responsible to identify data and metadata and facilitate the actual flow. It has two interfaces (*D_iStSyncLR*, *D_iStSyncDMan*). The *Data Manager* is responsible for handling the information flow either as file or stream and enable data and metadata transformation by different services provided by the **Service Layer**. The last component is the *Central Store*. It is responsible to store the actual information (data and metadata) using *D_iDManCSt* interface.

2.4 Security Layer

As presented in Figure 2-1 (see chapter 2), the **Security Layer (S)** serves all layers. It ensures that the data and metadata are accessible to the intended recipient (individual end users or groups) in a secure manner. The **Security Layer** consist of the following components as described in Figure 2-7.

Figure 2-7. Security Layer structure

The main goals of the *Security Manager* are to facilitate the authentication and authorization mechanisms for the end users, encryption of critical data, and monitoring of the state of the whole system from the security perspective.

2.4.1 Authentication

Authentication plays an important role for the whole infrastructure. Resources must be accessible for different groups of users, and access mechanisms must be clear and easy for everyone. The NFDI4Cat infrastructure consists of a high number of components (e.g. local repositories, central repository), where every component provides an authentication possibility. The authentication mechanisms must be similar (or better – the same) in all cases.

It is planned to realize different authentication mechanisms⁷ like local accounts, authentication based on standardized protocols and to investigate applicability of multi-factor authentication.

- 1. Local accounts** (user name and password) – will be used as starting point during the test phase of the infrastructure. It is a simple method, but it does not provide high

⁷ Authentication mechanisms, overview. <https://frontegg.com/blog/authentication>, accessed on 15.09.2022.

security and comfort. That's why for the production this method should be switched to another more sophisticated one.

2. Authentication based on standardized authentication protocols – this approach will be used as the main authentication mechanism, which will allow users to authenticate using already available accounts, e.g. institutional account at the university or an account in a social service like ORCID⁸. This approach is more secure and brings more comfort to the users.

Examples of such an approach could be:

- o **Shibboleth** – an implementation of the Security Assertion Markup Language (SAML) protocol, used currently by institutional identity management systems. This mechanism is usually supported by repository software (e.g. by Dataverse⁹, DSpace¹⁰) what makes it as an important candidate for NFDI4Cat infrastructure.
- o **OAuth 2.0 (Open Authorization)** – an open standard authorization protocol based on tokenization. Basing on the access tokens it allows to share with the third-party services (in our case - NFDI4Cat infrastructure) a specific account information (e.g. an institutional account or an ORCID ID) without sharing of passwords¹¹. This protocol is used by many services (e.g. ORCID¹², Dataverse¹³), has good security and allows also to get an authorization information.
- o **OpenID Connect (OIDC)** – an identity authentication protocol (authentication layer) based on top of the OAuth 2.0 protocol. It is used only for authentication and it implements some additional functionality compared to OAuth 2.0. OIDC is widely supported by many services (e.g. Dataverse¹⁴, DSpace¹⁵). ORCID is currently adapting this technology.¹⁶

3. Multi-factor authentication (MFA) - this approach combines different authentication methods and forces the user to go through authentication procedure on different places (different authentication factors). As an example – authentication via password (first factor) and then following authentication via some device (e.g. smartphone), where the user has to generate (or receive) a special code (second factor), which must be verified by the system. This can improve security and makes it much more difficult for attackers to compromise accounts.¹⁷

Multi-factor authentication methods play an important role for security, that's why they will be investigated during the development of the NFDI4Cat infrastructure.

⁸ ORCID, about page. <https://info.orcid.org/what-is-orcid/>, accessed on 15.09.2022.

⁹ Dataverse and Shibboleth. <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/installation/shibboleth.html>, accessed on 15.09.2022.

¹⁰ DSpace and Shibboleth. <https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/DSDOC7x/Authentication+Plugins#AuthenticationPlugins-ShibbolethAuthentication>, accessed on 15.09.2022.

¹¹ OAuth 2.0. <https://frontegg.com/blog/authentication#OAuth-2.0>, accessed on 15.09.2022.

¹² ORCID and OAuth 2.0. https://info.orcid.org/documentation/api-tutorials/api-tutorial-get-and-authenticated-orcid-id/#Implement_OAuth, accessed on 15.09.2022.

¹³ Dataverse and OAuth 2.0. <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/installation/oauth2.html>, accessed on 15.09.2022.

¹⁴ Dataverse and OIDC. <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/installation/oidc.html>, accessed on 15.09.2022.

¹⁵ DSpace and OIDC. [https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/DSDOC7x/Authentication+Plugins#AuthenticationPlugins-OpenIDConnect\(OIDC\)Authentication](https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/DSDOC7x/Authentication+Plugins#AuthenticationPlugins-OpenIDConnect(OIDC)Authentication), accessed on 15.09.2022.

¹⁶ ORCID and OIDC. <https://info.orcid.org/orcid-openid-connect-and-implicit-authentication/>, accessed on 15.09.2022.

¹⁷ Types of authentication, multi-factor authentication. <https://frontegg.com/blog/authentication#Types-of-Authentication>, accessed on 15.09.2022.

2.4.2 Authorization

When authentication is responsible for verifying the identity of a user, process, or device, authorization decides, what exactly is allowed for this user, process or device.¹⁸

Among all collected requirements (user stories) there are some explicit request to create different user groups, to share data or provide access to the data only for some users or user groups.

There are also some special requirements about legal aspects – implementation of the cool-off model (which is the topic of the task area 7 within the NFDI4Cat project) for the published data should be done with a consideration of security aspects like authorization and proper licensing of the data – what exactly can users do with the data published via the cool-off model.

All these requirements force developers to implement proper authorization mechanisms. As a basic authorization approach is planned to use the **discretionary access control (DAC)** method – determination of privileges depending on the specific users and their access groups.¹⁹

It is planned to implement the DAC method directly in the repositories (local and central). Usually, repository software already has some mechanisms of user access, e.g. via creation of user groups and providing them specific roles. However, the roles have different access rights.

It will be investigated, how exactly the described above authentication mechanisms can be combined with the DAC authorization method.

2.4.3 Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure in NFDI

It is planned, that the NFDI4Cat project as a member of NFDI consortia (National Research Data Infrastructure) will be also involved in the working group inside the section “Common Infrastructures”²⁰, which aims to develop a common mechanism of authentication and authorization for the entire NFDI consortia. It is planned to create a so-called **Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI)**, which should connect researchers also on the European level. During the implementation of own authentication and authorization mechanisms NFDI4Cat will consider the results of the NFDI working group and will use the newly developed NFDI-AAI mechanisms if possible.

2.4.4 Encryption

Since data is considered as the new oil, it has become the most important asset. It is imperative to shield sensitive or confidential data and keep it secure and protected from cyber theft.²¹ NFDI4Cat will try to abide by the EU directive of General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)²², as defined by article 5, to protect **Data-at-Rest**²³, **Data-in-Motion**²⁴ and **Data-in-Use**²⁵.

¹⁸ Authentication vs authorization. <https://frontegg.com/blog/authentication-vs-authorization>, accessed on 15.09.2022.

¹⁹ Authorization methods (see related chapter). <https://frontegg.com/blog/authentication-vs-authorization>, accessed on 15.09.2022.

²⁰ NFDI Section Common Infrastructures. <https://www.nfdi.de/section-infra/?lang=en>, accessed on 15.09.2022.

²¹ Sure ways to fail in data security. <https://www.endpointprotector.com/blog/sure-ways-to-fail-in-data-security/>, accessed on 20.09.2022.

²² General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the European Union. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/2016-05-04>, accessed on 20.09.2022.

²³ Data-at-Rest. <https://www.endpointprotector.com/blog/how-to-protect-your-data-at-rest/>, accessed on 15.09.2022.

²⁴ Data-in-Motion. <https://www.endpointprotector.com/blog/how-to-protect-data-in-motion/>, accessed on 15.09.2022.

²⁵ Data-in-Use. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Data_in_use, accessed on 20.09.2022.

- **Data-at-Rest** is the inactive data that is stored physically in digital form (e.g. databases, tapes, off-site backup etc.)
- **Data-in-Motion** is the information that flows over the public or untrusted network.
- **Data-in-Use** is the data which is stored on a non-persistent way, e.g. in the random access memory (RAM) of the computer or in the processor cache.

In NFDI4Cat, as far as possible, all **Data-in-Motion** will be secured with TLS encryption as it simplifies the end-user experience by masking the fact that the information is encrypted. **Data-at-Rest** will be protected with the help of Advanced Encryption Standard (AES)²⁶ using 256-bit key length. Furthermore, all encryption keys will be managed by Key Management Service (KMS). All backup data and off-site data will be secured with asymmetric cryptography. To prevent issues²⁷ with **Data-in-Use** a good continuous monitoring of the resources is needed – that can reduce the possibility of an intrusion via cold boot attacks, malicious hardware devices, rootkits and bootkits.

2.4.5 Monitoring

To keep all components of the NFDI4Cat architecture steady and secure, a proper monitoring mechanism is needed. Basing on terms and conditions (developed in task area 7 of NFDI4Cat), it should include the monitoring of available access events to the system (monitoring and visualization of log files), health-check monitoring of all important components on every architecture layer (e.g. authentication, authorization and encryption components on the **Security Layer**; metadata manager, harvester, PID manager and other components on the **Service Layer** etc.) and also continuous monitoring of all physical and virtual machines (hosts) to detect possible hacker attacks.

It is planned to investigate the market to find the most suitable software products to fulfill all requirements related to monitoring. As candidates could be Telegraf/InfluxDB/Grafana (TIG stack)²⁸, checkmk²⁹ etc.

Important note: NFDI4Cat will provide monitoring only for the centrally hosted components (central repository).

²⁶ Advanced Encryption Standard (AES). https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Advanced_Encryption_Standard, accessed on

²⁷ Data-in-Use concerns. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Data_in_use#Concerns, accessed on 20.09.2022.

²⁸ TIG Stack, Telegraf/InfluxDB/Grafana. <https://medium.com/@hoanglc/tig-stack-powerful-monitoring-tool-822521dce102>, accessed on 15.09.2022.

²⁹ Checkmk, monitoring solution. <https://checkmk.com/de/produkt/editionen>, accessed on 15.09.2022.

2.5 Summary of the Architecture Specification

Based on the aforementioned description, Figure 2-8 depicts the overall interaction between all the layers. Implementation details about individual components will be explained in details below.

Figure 2-8. NFDI4Cat Detail Design structure

Part 2: Detailed Design

While Part 1 focuses on the high-level design and general aspects of the system architecture, Part 2 provides a more in-depth, applied approach. It covers the detailed design of the various components, including the Meta Portal, Central Repository, Local Repositories, Semantic Repository, Persistent Identifier (PID) manager, and Deployment. The chapter includes specific information about the different tools, storage systems, and deployment strategies, providing practical insights into the implementation of the system.

3. Meta Portal

The meta portal is used as a main point for accessing and utilizing metadata harvested from the repositories within the infrastructure. Its microservice architecture offers flexibility as well as scalability. It subdivides into multiple sub-components which serve a special purpose within the overall structure of the meta portal.

The main purpose of the meta portal is to store the harvested metadata and enable browsing through this data. Therefore, the main component addresses **storage and exploration (Hub)**. According to the requirements, there are additional sub-components addressing the need for **metric tools, analysis tools, statistic tools** as well as **visualization** and **community tools**.

As shown in Figure 3-1, each of these sub-components is highly depended on the component responsible for storing and exploration. The shown structure displays a coarse representation of the meta portal components and their interaction. The following chapters will contain a more detailed description of each subcomponent and their interaction with the Hub.

The chosen candidate for implementing the meta portal is **Piveau** by FOKUS³⁰, that already implements the functionality needed and provides the ability to easily integrate additional functionalities required for overall statistics and data metrics.

Figure 3-1. Meta portal and its subcomponents

³⁰ Piveau. <https://www.piveau.de/> accessed on 19.09.2022.

3.1 Storage and Exploration (Hub)

The main components purpose is to store the harvested metadata and make it searchable so it can be further used by other components. Therefore, the component implements a basic **Storage Layer** including a triplestore³¹ for storing metadata, a filestore/database for storing binary files and a search engine for indexing the metadata.

The metaportal utilizes metadata using RDF based on the DCAT-AP specification. This specification defines semantic profiles for data catalogues including data sets and distributions. Furthermore, specific properties and their semantic representation are defined. Since pure DCAT-AP might not be sufficient to describe catalytic data it will be extended by additional definitions suitable for the usage within NFDI4Cat.

Figure 3-2. Metadata between all services within the hub

Figure 3-2 show the overall flow of metadata within the hub. The **registry** microservice is used as middleware and interacts with the triplestore. Its purpose is to preprocess the data received from the exporter and harmonize it to ensure integrity and traceability. The **registry** is supporting major RDF serializations through a RESTful interface.

This processed RDF data is then used by the **indexing** service which manages the high performance search index. The received data is flattened into JSON, which is more suitable for indexing and searching. This process supports well-defined and well-maintained support for vocabularies and ontologies and therefore is the place to integrate the developed ontologies of NFDI4Cat.

At the end, there are multiple endpoints for accessing the data. The triplestore exposes a SPARQL-endpoint to access the raw data. Furthermore, a RESTful API provides access to the RDF-serialized data as well as to the indexed serialization of the data. This API is also used by the GUI to access and display the stored data.

³¹ TripleStore, Jack Risher, Simple Knowledge Organization System § SWAD-Europe (2002–2004), Workshop on Semantic Web Storage and Retrieval – Position Papers.

3.2 Metrics Tool

The meta portal additionally should provide the possibility to assess the quality of the acquired metadata. This quality assessment is the task of the metrics tool, which will be provided as microservice containing nested services managing different tasks. Piveau's already existing implementation of a metrics tool utilizes rules and definitions provided by DCAT-AP³². These rules can be used or adapted depending on the results of the responsible Task Area within NFDI4Cat (Task Area 3).

The tool includes a **validator** service that tests the metadata against predefined rules. After the validation the **URL checker** tests the accessibility of URL included within the metadata. After these tests the **DQV annotator** produces a qualitative assessment of the metadata set based on a given metric scheme. The **validators** results will be saved within the triplestore linked to the corresponding metadata set.

Additionally, the **reporter** service sums up the results into a human-readable format. Therefore, all results will be extracted from the triplestore. The resulting report is available as document.

Figure 3-3. Schema of interaction of the metrics tools

3.3 Analysis Tool

Similar to the metrics tool, the **analysis tool** is more of a **toolbox** than just a singular tool. As shown in figure 3-4, the toolbox contains a set of microservices where each of them is used for a specific purpose or scientific analysis. These analyses will be carried out on the stored metadata and therefore utilize the data in the **Storage Layer** of the hub. The tools also provide a GUI which will be embedded into the overall GUI of the meta portal.

³² DCAT-AP. <https://www.dcat-ap.de/>, accessed on 19.09.2022.

Figure 3-4. Schema of interaction of analysis tools with the metaportal storage layer

3.4 Statistics Tool

The purpose of using this tool is to provide overall statistics of the data stored within the meta portal. In contrary to the analysis tools this tool won't operate statistics on the provided metadata but rather perform statistics depending on defined filters and conditions to extract the number of data sets available. Similar to the analysis toolbox this tool is implemented as a microservice that utilizes the hub's data and displays its results via a GUI embedded into the overall GUI of the meta portal.

3.5 Community Tool

The community tool should enable the users to interact with each other on the provided data. This could be reflected by the possibility to comment on data, to rate or to simply share it. Depending on the complexity of the task, the community tool will be either a toolbox of numerous tools or a general tool combining the functionality of all needed tools within itself. This tool will be implemented, similar to the other tools, as microservice which utilizes the data storage of the hub (and maybe add another database to it) and which results are displayed through a GUI embedded into the overall GUI.

3.6 Visualization Tool

Similar to the metrics tool or analysis tool, the **visualization tool** is more of a **toolbox** than just a singular tool. Each visualization technique is encapsulated within a microservice. Since these visualization tools should display characteristics based on the available metadata they utilize the **Storage Layer** of the hub. The tools provide a GUI which will be embedded into the overall GUI of the meta portal.

3.7 Meta Portal Harvester (Repository Harvester)

The **repository harvester** serves the purpose of collecting metadata from various endpoints for the meta portal. The chosen solution to implement this service would be **Piveau Consus** by FOKUS.

The harvester uses a microservices architecture which means, that each process within the harvester is executed by a microservice whereby some processes can have multiple instances of a microservice adapted to special specifications. The harvester consists of four microservices: a scheduler, an importer, a transformer and an exporter.

Figure 3-5. Flow of metadata through the services of the repository harvester

Figure 3-5 shows the metadata flow within the microservices of the harvester. The overall starting point are different sources where metadata is provided by institutions. Those sources might have different standards or interfaces for retrieving the metadata as well as different metadata schemas.

To harvest the provided metadata from various repositories within the infrastructure an **importer** is needed. Each endpoint/standard requires a new instance of the importer microservice, adapted to the given specifications. Some standards/endpoints are already covered:

- CKAN
- OAI-PMH
- uData
- RDF
- SPARQL

To orchestrate the list of all importers the **scheduler** microservice is used. Within this service the execution time and its periodicity for each importer is defined.

The metaportal utilizes metadata using RDF based on the DCAT-AP specification. This specification defines semantic profiles for data catalogues including data sets and distributions. Furthermore, specific properties and their semantic representation are defined. Since pure DCAT-AP might not be sufficient to describe catalytic data it will be extended by additional definitions suitable for the usage within NFDI4Cat.

Since not every given repository or source provides metadata using RDF complying to DCAT-AP (or an extended version of it) an additional microservice is needed: the **transformer**. It converts the metadata retrieved as key-value pairs into the target format (RDF) - if not already available as a RDF serialization. In parallel to converting the given metadata to RDF it also gets converted to comply to DCAT-AP (or an extended version of it). Also, aggregations or anonymizations are possible if needed. Similar to the importer microservice, the transformer also offers the ability to use different instances to convert the delivered data from a specific format to a RDF serialization. There are two format transformers already available:

- javascript to RDF
- xslt to RDF

The last step within this flow of metadata is the **exporter**. The exporter uploads the collected and transformed metadata to the meta portal. Since all transformations and conversions are already done, only one instance of the exporter is needed.

4. Central Repository

The central repository will deal as a common solution to store data of every partner. The software for the central repository will be chosen according to the collected requirements concerning e.g. easy way to access and provided functionality. Figure 4-1 shows the general structure of the repository components and their interactions.

Figure 4-1. Structure of the central repository components and their interactions

To simplify the deployment of the central repository, different existing software solutions are evaluated for all components on each layer. All experiments are currently being carried out on the virtualization platform bwCloud³³ (Infrastructure-as-a-Service platform for scientists in Baden-Wuerttemberg, Germany). As the list of selected software candidates is not finalized yet,

³³ bwCloud, Infrastructure-as-a-Service, IaaS. <https://www.bw-cloud.org/>, accessed on 20.09.2022.

it is difficult to predict, how the deployment of all these components can look like on the real infrastructure.

The importance of a central repository lies in its ability to efficiently organize, store and provide access to a large amount of data. By having a central location for data storage, it eliminates the need for multiple, dispersed locations for data storage, which can make it difficult for users to find and access the data they need. This leads to a more streamlined and efficient process for accessing and managing data. Additionally, a central repository can also ensure data integrity and security, by providing backups and ensuring proper access controls are in place.

5. Local Repositories

While the central repository will fulfill most of the collected user requirements, there are some special cases which require a separate repository (or a repository with a custom configuration). For such cases NFDI4Cat provides the concept of local repositories.

A local repository is a repository, which will be (or already is) created specifically for the requirements of one individual partner. It is a completely separated instance with own users, administrators. Such an instance may also be hosted separately from the central repository - on the local resources of the partners.

Despite all locality and independence of the local repositories, all local repositories will be tightly integrated into the NFDI4Cat infrastructure. Communication between local repositories, the central repository and the meta portal will be organized via special protocols. With a help of the meta portal NFDI4Cat will try to connect all publicly available data and metadata in all repositories (local and central) providing global search possibility for the users.

Hosting of local repositories

In the initial phase of the NFDI4Cat project, the main focus is put on the investigation and installation of the central repository. All experience and intermediate results from this phase will be used later on for the preparation of local repositories. It is important to mention that NFDI4Cat administrators of the central repository will not be responsible for the installation and hosting of any local repository. This will be done locally by the partners. However, the administrators of the central NFDI4Cat repository will share their experience and will provide support for the partners on all repository-related aspects.

In terms of support and hosting of local repositories there are currently some directions, which should be discussed during the project life cycle:

1. **Providing of the repository installation images.** During the test phase of the central repository some virtual machines with different repository software were prepared. Such images could deal as a starting point for the installation of local repositories.
2. **Hosting possibilities for repositories.** In the project will be discussed, if the NFDI4Cat infrastructure can be used also as a hosting platform for the local repositories.
3. **Hosting possibilities for data.** In the project will be discussed, if the NFDI4Cat infrastructure can be used for hosting of only data for the repositories. It means, that the data could be physically stored on the NFDI4Cat resources and then connected to the

externally hosted local repositories (as a remote storage like NFS³⁴, BeeGFS³⁵, S3³⁶ etc.).

Requirements on local repositories

As the communication between all components of the NFDI4Cat infrastructure plays an important role, all components must have an agreement on the communication mechanisms and protocols. It is planned to use a standard communication protocol, e.g. the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH³⁷) if feasible. All local repositories and the central repository should support at least OAI-PMH to allow harvesting of metadata by the meta portal.

For the usage of some specific custom created tools all repositories should support some API, e.g. REST³⁸, or the common deposit protocol SWORD³⁹. Such an API will allow communication with repositories externally via HTTP protocol directly via command line and special requests. Usually, different repository software has custom REST-API. Generally developed tools will only support APIs according to the OpenAPI⁴⁰ standard.

All mentioned above requirements are usually supported by any kind of repository software. More specific requirements will be discussed with the project partners individually directly before the installation of the repositories.

Providing backups and ensuring proper access controls is required from the local repositories hosts. This process ensures valuable data is not lost in case of failures and provides a way to quickly restore systems.

6. Semantic Repository

As it was already mentioned in Chapters 2.2.2, 2.2.4, 2.2.5, a complex representation of metadata plays an important role for the NFDI4Cat project. The NFDI4Cat project has created a new ontology, which will enable the representation and semantic interlinking of the metadata within the Resource Description Framework (RDF) data model.

Unfortunately, currently tested repository software solutions do not support the RDF technology on a full scale, they can not provide a complete RDF functionality to the users. Usually only standard static and limited metadata blocks are supported by them, what makes it almost impossible the idea to describe all relations in an efficient and flexible way. It also means, that some additional software solutions for metadata in RDF is needed - some semantic repository.

A semantic repository is a repository, where the metadata can be stored, represented and accessed within the RDF data model. It allows a complex search within all available metadata, high flexibility and extendibility of the metadata.

³⁴ NFS, Network File System. https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Network_File_System, accessed on 14.12.2022.

³⁵ BeeGFS parallel file system. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/BeeGFS>, accessed on 14.12.2022.

³⁶ S3, Simple Storage Service. https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Amazon_Web_Services#Speicher, accessed on

³⁷ OAI-PMH. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_Archives_Initiative, accessed on 19.12.2022.

³⁸ REST, Representational State Transfer. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Representational_state_transfer, accessed on 19.12.2022.

³⁹ SWORD, Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/SWORD_\(protocol\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/SWORD_(protocol)), accessed on 19.12.2022.

⁴⁰ OpenAPI specification. <https://swagger.io/specification/>, accessed on 19.01.2023.

It is planned to investigate different software solutions for semantic repositories like Wikibase⁴¹, Virtuoso⁴², DBpedia⁴³, Apache Jena⁴⁴ etc. An additional challenge will be an establishment of relations between traditional repositories (where the physical data with some basic metadata will be stored) and semantic repositories (where the complex metadata in RDF will be stored) to allow the users one common area to work with the data and metadata.

7. Persistent Identifier (PID) manager

The PID manager will use the handle system as technical basis⁴⁵. The handle system has very loose rules regarding the data that is stored in the handle records and also how PID-suffixes are constructed. Moreover, the support for authentication/authorization is limited. Due to these limitations a handle server is typically not exposed to the users directly but hidden behind a gateway. In typical RDM installations the repository software functions as a gateway to the handle-server. However, in NFDI4Cat it is planned to provide PIDs also to the local pilots (e.g. an ELN). For this purpose, a simple (e.g. REST) interface for CRUD⁴⁶ operations on PIDs is also needed. Recently so called “typed PIDs” have been introduced that allow defining schema-based rules for the PID-suffix and for all other data in PID records (including the PID record structure itself)⁴⁷. Typed PIDs are not part of the handle-system itself but have to be implemented separately.

In NFDI4Cat it is planned to use these modern “typed PIDs” for several purposes:

- PIDs for data objects in the repository software (it will be investigated, how typed PIDs can be integrated into the workflow of the repository software)
- PIDs for ontologies and terminologies (but not for the concepts in them)
- PIDs for samples, instruments etc.

NFDI4Cat will request a single handle-prefix so that all PIDs are created in the same top-level namespace. A separation of PIDs by the different use cases will be realized by using typed PIDs with different PID-suffix-rules. Details about the generation of the PID-suffixes and about which metadata are stored in the PID records are still in discussion.

In December 2022 a new software tool “Typed PID creator”⁴⁸ was released that will be tested as gateway to the handle-server. This software provides a REST interface to CRUD operation on PIDs and should support jwt-authorisation. In addition, it integrates validation of PIDs against PID-schemas (also called “kernel information profiles”).

An overview of the PID manager components is given in Figure 7-1.

⁴¹ Wikibase. <https://wikiba.se/>, accessed on 19.12.2022.

⁴² Virtuoso. <https://virtuoso.openlinksw.com/>, accessed on 19.12.2022.

⁴³ DBpedia. <https://www.dbpedia.org/>, accessed on 19.12.2022.

⁴⁴ Apache Jena. <https://jena.apache.org/>, accessed on 19.12.2022.

⁴⁵ Handle PID service. <https://handle.net/>, accessed on 18.01.2023.

⁴⁶ CRUD operations: create, read, update and delete. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Create,_read,_update_and_delete, accessed on 19.01.2023.

⁴⁷ PID information types. <https://rd-alliance.org/group/pid-information-types-wg/outcomes/pid-information-types>, accessed on 18.01.2023.

⁴⁸ Typed PID creator, software tool. <https://kit-data-manager.github.io/webpage/typed-pid-maker/index.html>, accessed on 18.01.2023.

Figure 7-1. Scheme of PID manager and PID use cases⁴⁹

8. Deployment

In this chapter the main aspects of the deployment of the most important components of the NFDI4Cat infrastructure are described.

8.1 Meta Portal

For now only some general deployment information of the metaportal can be described, which include:

- Linux Server running docker-compose as service for hosting meta portal
- Each service included in the meta portal is run as a docker container within a docker network
- Automated deployment via GitLab pipeline

For the most components it is planned to describe their deployment mechanisms and their technology readiness level (TRL)⁵⁰ only during the next iteration of the architecture document.

8.2 Central Repository

The central repository will be deployed in a phase manner. It will use Infrastructure As Code (IaC) strategy to automate deployment, provisioning, and configuration. The overall deployment will be completed in three stages.

In the *first stage* a base repository with the following software components will be deployed.

- Application server

⁴⁹ Source code of figure. <https://gitlab.fokus.fraunhofer.de/nfdi4cat/pid-development/crid/-/issues/1>, accessed on 18.01.2023.

⁵⁰ Technology readiness levels (TRLs). https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Technology_readiness_level, accessed on 20.09.2022.

An application server provides a software framework that facilitates the hosting of Web applications and an environment to run them. Examples include Tomcat⁵¹, nginx⁵², nodejs⁵³ etc.

- Middleware

A middleware enables existing software to help manage the complexity and heterogeneity inherent in distributed systems. It is a piece of software that provides a common programming abstraction across a distributed system. The goal is to support and simplify complex distributed applications. Examples for the purpose of the central repository include Apache Solr⁵⁴, Elasticsearch⁵⁵, message-broker software etc.

- Database

A database is a software used to organize and manage information. Management of information involves both defining structures for storage of information and providing mechanisms for the manipulation of information. In addition, the database must ensure the safety of the information stored, despite system crashes or attempts at unauthorized access. If data are to be shared among several users, the system must avoid possible anomalous results. Databases in a traditional infrastructure stack is a relational database management system (RDBMS). Example includes Postgresql⁵⁶, MySQL⁵⁷, MariaDB⁵⁸ etc

Each of the aforementioned software components will be selected after the completion for the currently on-going software testing exercise.

In the *second stage* the deployed central repository will be updated to address the following:

- Identity Management

Securing user access plays a key role in the exchange of information. In today's always connected generation, digital information is becoming ever more valuable. Access protection must therefore meet increasingly strict requirements. Chapter 2.4 describes some of the solution that are currently being looked at for Identity management for the central repository.

- Persistence Identifiers

In order to distinctly identify an object, it needs to have an universally unique identifier (UUID). A good example is a published books with its International Standard Book Number (ISBN). In this age of rapid digitization it is imperative to uniquely identify digital object as well. Some of the well know techniques used in industry to uniquely identify digital object is Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) and Handle.

- Semantic Data Management

⁵¹ Tomcat. <https://tomcat.apache.org/>, accessed on 20.12.2022.

⁵² Nginx. <https://www.nginx.com/>, accessed on 20.12.2022.

⁵³ Node.js. <https://nodejs.org/en/>, accessed on 20.12.2022.

⁵⁴ Apache Solr. <https://solr.apache.org/>, accessed on 20.12.2022.

⁵⁵ Elasticsearch. <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch/>, accessed on 20.12.2022.

⁵⁶ Postgresql. <https://www.postgresql.org/>, accessed on 20.12.2022.

⁵⁷ MySQL. <https://www.mysql.com/de/>, accessed on 20.12.2022.

⁵⁸ MariaDB. <https://mariadb.org/>, accessed on 20.12.2022.

Making sense of data is both important and increasingly challenging. The goal is to enhance the Web by linking the data and enriching it with metadata in ways that facilitate the understanding of data and the exploitation of the same. Some example that can be used for semantic management include Apache Jena⁵⁹, Virtuoso⁶⁰ etc..

Each of the aforementioned components will be selected and adapted after the completion for the software testing exercise and an agreement within the consortium.

In the *third stage* the central repository will be tested for

- connectivity to external local repositories
- connectivity to external data harvesters

At the end of these three stages the central repository will adhere to technology readiness level 7 that will help us to demonstrate the overall system in operational environment.

⁵⁹ Apache Jena. <https://jena.apache.org/>, accessed on 20.12.2022.

⁶⁰ Virtuoso. <https://virtuoso.openlinksw.com/>, accessed on 20.12.2022.

Concluding remarks

In conclusion, the Architecture Document is a milestone, providing an overview of the current framework. Published as our initial working document, it's the foundation for collaborative work with the NFDI4Cat community. Considering the dynamic field and community spirit, we expect ongoing refinements to this living document.

Upcoming version(s) of the Architecture Document will not only implement valuable changes but also integrate insights from the NFDI4Cat working groups, ensuring a responsive evolution of the proposed framework. Furthermore, upon the integration of the components outlined in this document into a unified system, detailed technical aspects of the integration process will be provided, ensuring a seamless and well-documented implementation.

References

[Mendes et al., 2020]

Mendes, P. S. F., Siradze, S., Pirro, L., & Thybaut, J. W. (2020). Open data in catalysis: From today's big picture to the future of small data. *ChemCatChem*, cctc.202001132. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cctc.202001132>.